

Emotion Dynamics - Second Draft

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What is this code?

This code is to get and clean the 3-Wave ESM data (Pe et al. 2016).

Before you proceed make sure you are familiar with `dplyr` and `tidyr` packages (included in `tidyverse` collection) and especially the pipe operator (i.e. `%>%`). I would strongly suggest going through Garrett Golemund's data wrangling tutorial or take a look at `tidyverse.org` documentations.

Loading packages

I first install and load the required packages (this is not included in the current report.)

Functions

Then it's time to define the functions we need. They include the following:

- `my.augmenter`: This function is meant to add NA in between days to account for the night lags. It takes the complete long data frame (cf. *data cleaning*) and, by default, adds one NA between the days. In order to add more NAs (for instance, for higher order AR modeling if needed) one should pass `number.of.NAs` in the arguments.

```
# my.augmenter ----
my.augmenter <- function(data.input, number.of.NAs = 1, wave = FALSE){

  pids <- data.input %>% select(PID) %>% unique() %>% t()
  data.new.null <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = dim(data.input)[2], nrow = 0))
  colnames(data.new.null) <- colnames(data.input)

  data.new <- data.new.null

  for (pid in pids) {
    empty.rows <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = dim(data.input)[2], nrow = number.of.NAs))
    colnames(empty.rows) <- colnames(data.input)
    empty.rows$PID <- pid
    empty.rows$MISS <- 1

    days <- data.input %>% filter(PID==pid) %>% select(D) %>% unique() %>% t()

    data.new.day <- data.new.null

    for (day in days) {
      data.day <- data.input %>% filter(PID==pid,D==day)
      data.new.day <- data.new.day %>% rbind(data.day,empty.rows)
    }

    new.beeps <- dim(data.new.day)[1]
    data.new.day$BEEP <- c(1:new.beeps)
```

```

data.new <- data.new %>% rbind(data.new.day)
}

this.wave <- wave
if(!wave) this.wave <- data.input %>% select(WAVE) %>% na.omit() %>% max()
data.new$WAVE <- this.wave

return(data.new)
}

```

- `my.agggregator`: This function is responsible to build PA and NA constructs out of the 3 + 5 questions by averaging them according to `weights.pa` and `weights.na` vectors (default is simple average). By default, the function returns a with PID, BEEP, WAVE, MISS, POSA, and NEGA. In order to get a very concise table (i.e. only PA and NA scores) one should pass `only.scores = TRUE`. This function can include more questions in PA and NA if one passes `include.more = TRUE`, however, it has not been implemented yet. **Note** that it should be called after `my.augmenter` because it removes some columns needed for augmentation.

```

# my.agggregator ----
my.agggregator <- function(data.input, weights.pa = c(1,1,1), weights.na = c(1,1,1,1,1),
                           only.scores = F, include.more = F){

cols.pa <- data.input %>% select(BLIJ:OPGEW)
cols.na <- data.input %>% select(DROEV:STRES)

POSA <- rowSums(cols.pa*weights.pa/sum(weights.pa))
NEGA <- rowSums(cols.na*weights.na/sum(weights.na))

data.output <- data.input %>% select(PID, BEEP, WAVE, MISS) %>% cbind(POSA, NEGA)

if(only.scores){return(data.output %>% select(POSA, NEGA))}

return(data.output)
}

```

- `my.ar.r2`: It calculates R^2 of the Autoregression model of order `ar.order` (default to 1, higher orders not implemented yet) for the last two columns of `input.data`, which could be the POSA and NEGA or C1 and C2. The `input.data` must have PID and WAVE columns. If `return.means = FALSE` it returns the whole table of R^2 for with `R2.C1`, `R2.C2`, `R2.avg` columns (the third one is the average of the first two columns), otherwise it only returns mean of the aforementioned columns. For the time being, it uses non-hierarchical AR models (to change that, set `hierarchical = TRUE`, not implemented yet though.)

```

# AR.R2 to calculate AR residuals ----
my.ar.r2 <- function(input.data, hierarchical = F, return.means = T, ar.order = 1){

# This function works on the last two columns of input.data
index.C1 <- dim(input.data)[2]-1
index.C2 <- dim(input.data)[2]

pids <- input.data$PID %>% unique()
pid.num <- pids %>% t() %>% length()

R2 <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 3, nrow = 0))
colnames(R2) <- c("R2.C1", "R2.C2", "R2.avg")

```

```

if(hierarchical){}
else{
  for (wave in 1:3) {
    for (i in 1:pid.num) {
      row.num <- i + (wave-1)*pid.num
      # print(row.num)
      working.data.tmp <- input.data %>% filter(PID==pids[i],WAVE==wave) %>%
        select(index.C1, index.C2)
      num.obs <- dim(working.data.tmp)[1]

      lm.data <- data.frame(matrix(nrow = (num.obs-1), ncol = 4))
      colnames(lm.data) <- c("C1", "C2", "C1.lag.1", "C2.lag.1")

      x <- sapply(working.data.tmp[,1], function(x) sum(!is.na(x))) %>% sum() %>% sum()
      if(x==0) next #to skip those person-waves where all the items are NAs

      lm.data[,1:2] <- working.data.tmp[2:num.obs,]
      lm.data[,3:4] <- working.data.tmp[1:(num.obs-1),]

      lm.C1 <- lm(C1 ~ C1.lag.1 + C2.lag.1, data=lm.data, na.action=na.exclude)
      lm.C2 <- lm(C2 ~ C1.lag.1 + C2.lag.1, data=lm.data, na.action=na.exclude)

      SSE.C1 <- lm.C1$residuals**2 %>% sum()
      SSE.C2 <- lm.C2$residuals**2 %>% sum()

      C1 <- lm.data$C1 %>% na.omit
      C2 <- lm.data$C2 %>% na.omit
      SSTot.C1 <- sum((C1-mean(C1))**2)
      SSTot.C2 <- sum((C2-mean(C2))**2)

      R2[row.num,1] <- R2.C1 <- 1 - SSE.C1/SSTot.C1
      R2[row.num,2] <- R2.C2 <- 1 - SSE.C2/SSTot.C2
      R2[row.num,3] <- (R2.C1+R2.C2)/2
    }
  }
}
if(return.means) return(colMeans(R2[,,na.rm=T])
else return(R2)
}

```

- `my.pca.aggregator`: This function is meant to transform the questions into two constructs (similar to POSA and NEGA) using principal component analysis (via `stats::prcomp`). To this end, the data frame of selected questions (cf. later under *Subsetting the answers*) is fed to `stats::prcomp` and the first `construct.dim` components (default 2, change with care, not fully implemented) are extracted. Then the rotation matrix is used to map the data into a two-dimensional construct. This function outputs its input data frame where the questions are all substituted with the mapped constructs, C1 and C2.

```

# my.pca.aggregator to make POSA and NEGA ----
my.pca.aggregator <- function(input.data, construct.dim = 2){

  data.pca <- input.data %>% select(-1:-4)
  sample.pca <- data.pca %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=construct.dim)

  data.rotated <- scale(data.pca, sample.pca$center, sample.pca$scale) %*%

```

```

sample.pca$rotation

if(construct.dim==2) colnames(data.rotated) <- c("C1","C2")

output.data <- input.data %>% select(1:4) %>% cbind(data.rotated)

return(output.data)
}

```

- my.summarizer: it make a data frame of means, standard deviations, autocorrelations, MSSD's of C1 and C2, and correlation of C1 and C2. If report.AC=FALSE it will calculate autoregressions instead of autocorrelations (not implemented yet). lag.max (default 1) decides about the number of lags for AC or AR.

```

my.summarizer <- function(input.data, lag.max = 1, report.AC = TRUE){

pids <- input.data$PID %>% unique()
pid.num <- pids %>% t() %>% length()

summaries <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 11, nrow = pid.num*3))
colnames(summaries) <- c("PID", "WAVE", "mean.C1", "mean.C2", "sd.C1", "sd.C2",
                        "ac.C1", "ac.C2", "mssd.C1", "mssd.C2", "corr")

for (i in 1:pid.num) {
  for (wave in 1:3) {
    row.num <- i + (wave-1)*pid.num

    summaries$PID[row.num] <- pids[i]
    summaries$WAVE[row.num] <- wave

    C1 <- data.avg %>% filter(PID==pids[i], WAVE==wave) %>% select(POSA)
    C2 <- data.avg %>% filter(PID==pids[i], WAVE==wave) %>% select(NEGA)

    summaries$mean.C1[row.num] <- C1 %>% na.omit() %>% t() %>% mean()
    summaries$mean.C2[row.num] <- C2 %>% na.omit() %>% t() %>% mean()

    summaries$sd.C1[row.num] <- C1 %>% na.omit() %>% t() %>% sd()
    summaries$sd.C2[row.num] <- C2 %>% na.omit() %>% t() %>% sd()

    if(report.AC){
      AC.C1 <- C1 %>% acf(na.action = na.pass, lag.max = 1, plot = F)
      AC.C2 <- C2 %>% acf(na.action = na.pass, lag.max = lag.max, plot = F)
      summaries$ac.C1[row.num] <- AC.C1$acf[2:lag.max] %>% na.omit() %>% mean()
      summaries$ac.C2[row.num] <- AC.C2$acf[2:lag.max] %>% na.omit() %>% mean()
    } else {
      # CHANGE THE CODE TO AR!
      AR.C1 <- C1 %>% acf(na.action = na.pass, lag.max = 1, plot = F)
      AR.C2 <- C2 %>% acf(na.action = na.pass, lag.max = lag.max, plot = F)
      summaries$ac.C1[row.num] <- AR.C1$acf[2:lag.max] %>% na.omit() %>% mean()
      summaries$ac.C2[row.num] <- AR.C2$acf[2:lag.max] %>% na.omit() %>% mean()
      colnames(summaries) <- c("PID", "WAVE", "mean.C1", "mean.C2", "sd.C1", "sd.C2",
                              "ar.C1", "ar.C2", "mssd.C1", "mssd.C2", "corr")
    }
  }
}

```

```

summaries$mssd.C1[row.num] <- C1 %>% mssd()
summaries$mssd.C2[row.num] <- C2 %>% mssd()

summaries$corr[row.num] <- cor(C1, C2, use="na.or.complete")
}
}
return(summaries)
}

```

- `my.dist.plot`: it plots density kernels of R^2 for two affect components (whether POSA and NEGA or PC1 and PC2) and adds the averages as vertical lines. By setting `is.den = FALSE` it will produce histograms instead of density curves. To change the name of the components on the plot pass `col.names` as an argument.

```

my.dist.plot <- function(input.ar, col.names = c("C1", "C2"), is.den = TRUE){

d <- dim(input.ar)[2]
data.tmp <- input.ar %>% select((d-2):(d))
colnames(data.tmp) <- c(col.names, paste("Mean of", col.names[1], col.names[2]))

means <- data.tmp %>% colMeans()
data.hist <- data.tmp %>% gather()

if(is.den){
  ggplot(data.hist, aes(x=value, fill=key)) + geom_density(alpha=0.25) +
    geom_vline(xintercept=means, linetype="dashed", size=.5) +
    labs(x="R2", y="density", fill="Components") + xlim(0,1)
} else{
  ggplot(data.hist, aes(x=value, fill=key)) + geom_histogram(alpha=0.25) +
    geom_vline(xintercept=means, linetype="dashed", size=.5) +
    labs(x="R2", y="density", fill="Components") + xlim(0,1)
}
}
}

```

Data cleaning and tidying

Too lazy to write details, the inline comments explain it to some extent. The variable `lags.night` defines how many night lags (NAs) `my.augmenter` adds between days. The following are the data frames which can be used later on. **Make sure** you do not overwrite them outside this chunk.

- `data.ESM.complete`: a long table of the whole 3-wave ESM dataset, with clean row names (`w1_` etc. removed).
- `data.ESM.complete.aug`: the same data frame as `data.ESM.complete` but with night lags and also without LT (since it was making unnecessary headaches when `rbind()`ing).
- `data.ESM.aug.clean`: basically it's `data.ESM.complete.aug` without the redundant columns, keeping PID, BEEP, WAVE, MISS, and the all the questions.
- `data.ESM.aug.concise`: basically `data.ESM.aug.clean` without the questions not directly related to the 8 emotions.
- `data.primary`: the data frame which will be used from now on. As of now, it's `data.ESM.aug.concise` but you may want to change it if you want to. **Note** that it shouldn't be touched outside this chunk. I also read the baseline data of the three waves but I do not use them in this code yet.

- `data.avg.simple`: the data frame of POSA and NEGAs built from simple averaging over 3 + 5 emotions.

```

# reading the raw data
path.data <- "../Datas/Pe et al (2016) - Three-wave ESM/"
data.ESM.raw <- read_sav(paste0(path.data, "Longitudinal.sav"))
data.baseline.wave1.raw <- read_sav(paste0(path.data, "wave_1_main.sav"))
data.baseline.wave2.raw <- read_sav(paste0(path.data, "wave_2_main.sav"))
data.baseline.wave3.raw <- read_sav(paste0(path.data, "wave_3_main.sav"))

colnames(data.ESM.raw) <- toupper(colnames(data.ESM.raw))

# saving waves separately
data.ESM.wave1.raw <- data.ESM.raw %>% select(PID, TRIGGER, contains("W1"))
data.ESM.wave2.raw <- data.ESM.raw %>% select(PID, TRIGGER, contains("W2"))
data.ESM.wave3.raw <- data.ESM.raw %>% select(PID, TRIGGER, contains("W3"))

# Make sure the NA's in WAVE are not missed
data.ESM.wave1.raw[3] <- 1
data.ESM.wave2.raw[3] <- 2
data.ESM.wave3.raw[3] <- 3

# getting rid of _W1
data.ESM.wave1.raw <- data.ESM.wave1.raw %>%
  rename_at(.vars = vars(ends_with("_W1")), .funs = funs(sub("_W1$", "", .)))

# Making the colnames similar
colnames(data.ESM.wave1.raw)[3] <- "WAVE"
colnames(data.ESM.wave2.raw) <- colnames(data.ESM.wave1.raw)
colnames(data.ESM.wave3.raw) <- colnames(data.ESM.wave1.raw)

# augmenting the data with NA's after each day, will be useful in calculating AR etc.
# Change lags.night to increase the number of NA's between days
lags.night <- 1

data.ESM.wave1.aug <- data.ESM.wave1.raw %>%
  my.augmenter(number.of.NAs=lags.night, wave=1) %>% select(-LT)
data.ESM.wave2.aug <- data.ESM.wave2.raw %>%
  my.augmenter(number.of.NAs=lags.night, wave=2) %>% select(-LT)
data.ESM.wave3.aug <- data.ESM.wave3.raw %>%
  my.augmenter(number.of.NAs=lags.night, wave=3) %>% select(-LT)

# binding the rows to have a long table
data.ESM.complete <- rbind(data.ESM.wave1.raw, data.ESM.wave2.raw, data.ESM.wave3.raw)
data.ESM.complete.aug <- rbind(data.ESM.wave1.aug, data.ESM.wave2.aug, data.ESM.wave3.aug)

rm(data.ESM.wave1.raw, data.ESM.wave2.raw, data.ESM.wave3.raw)
rm(data.ESM.wave1.aug, data.ESM.wave2.aug, data.ESM.wave3.aug)

# getting rid of some columns
# change it in the select() function below to add more question
data.ESM.aug.clean <- data.ESM.complete.aug %>%
  select(PID, BEEP, WAVE, MISS, BLIJ:NEG, -GRID)
data.ESM.aug.concise <- data.ESM.aug.clean %>%
  select(PID, BEEP, WAVE, MISS, BLIJ:NEG)

```

```
# data.primary is the data frame we use from now on. Do not overwrite it later!
data.primary <- data.ESM.aug.clean

# Making a data frame out of simple averaging of the emotions
data.avg.simple <- data.primary %>% my.aggregator()
```

Here is a look into `data.avg.simple`:

Table 1: `data.avg.simple`: data frame of *POSA* and *NEGAs* built from simple averaging over 3 + 5 emotions.

PID	BEEP	WAVE	MISS	POSA	NEGA
101	1	1	0	68.66667	4.8
101	2	1	0	52.66667	8.8
101	3	1	0	61.00000	6.2
101	4	1	1	NA	NA
101	5	1	0	63.33333	5.0
101	6	1	0	39.66667	14.2
101	7	1	0	76.00000	6.6
101	8	1	0	75.00000	5.6
101	9	1	0	70.00000	3.8
101	10	1	0	45.00000	4.6

Getting insights into the data

This chunk is responsible for making the `summaries.simple.avg` data frame which includes mean, standard deviation, auto-correlation, and MSSD of PAs and NAs together with PA-NA correlations for each participants at each wave. These are used in the next chunk to plot correlation matrices of these values across waves. *Note* that since we needed an ad-hoc understanding of the data we used AC not AR. The AR will come into the picture later on.

In the end, I plotted the correlation matrices of `summaries.simple.avg` across waves. Since, given that we decided to take autoregression as the optimization criterion, this step is not really necessary anymore. Hence, I'm ignoring it with a `if` statement. Feel free to change the condition if you wanted to.

```
if(FALSE){
data.avg <- data.avg.simple

summaries.simple.avg <- data.avg %>% my.summarizer()

# Plotting the correlation of the summary statistics ----
for (summary.stat in 3:11) {
  summaries.simple.avg %>% select(PID,WAVE, summary.stat) %>% spread(WAVE,3) %>%
  select(-PID) %>% cor(use= "na.or.complete") %>%
  corrplot(method="square", title = colnames(summaries.simple.avg)[summary.stat])
}
}
```

AR(1), here it begins!

In this chunk we get an overview of how the R^2 of *POSA* and *NEGA* looks like.

```

ar1.r2.avg.simple <- data.avg.simple %>% my.ar.r2(return.means = F) %>% na.omit()
dist.avg.simple <- ar1.r2.avg.simple %>% my.dist.plot(col.names = c("POSA", "NEGA"))
dist.avg.simple

```


Doing PCA to find the *optimal* affect constructs

Now it's time to make the PCA thingy straight!

Overview

We thought about different ways of searching through the 'weights-space' (that's what I call it now). We agreed to first do a selection on the questions (see which questions to include in the construct) and then run a PCA to find a 2-dimensional construct (which would, hopefully, explain much of the variance). Then, by using applying AR(1) and calculating R-squared, we can compare different sets of questions (as well as 'the good/best' construct) according to the better stability.

Subsetting the answers

First I will try to make subsets of the 3 + 5 questions. The idea is there could be "noisy" questions in the data which do not contribute to reduction in R^2 of the AR model. PCA will later take care of combination (i.e. aggregation) of the questions into constructs.

Here I make a for loop to go over all combinations of simple selections of questions, i.e. the columns. The selection is carried out by using binary counter to filter the desired columns. Hard to explain, see the code!

After selecting the questions (i.e. columns) the data frame is passed to `my.pca.aggregator` and then to

AR.R2. The questions included in the PCA (and subsequently fed to AR.R2), coded as boolean (0 for excluded questions and 1 for those included), and the R^2 s are written in `ar1.r2.selected`.

```
start_time <- Sys.time()

questions <- colnames(data.primary)[5:12]

ar1.r2.selected <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = 11, nrow = 0))
colnames(ar1.r2.selected) <- c(questions, "R2.C1", "R2.C2", "R2.avg")

for (count.pos in 1:7){
  for (count.neg in 1:31) {
    row.num <- count.pos+(count.neg-1)*7
    bin.pos <- as.integer(intToBits(count.pos))[1:3]
    bin.neg <- as.integer(intToBits(count.neg))[1:5]

    bin.code <- c(bin.pos,bin.neg)

    selected.code <- bin.code*c(5:12)
    selected.code <- selected.code[selected.code!=0]

    data.primary.selected <- data.primary %>% select(PID:MISS,selected.code)

    ar1.r2.selected[row.num,9:11] <- data.primary.selected %>%
      my.pca.aggregator() %>% my.ar.r2()
    ar1.r2.selected[row.num,1:8] <- bin.code
    #   print(row.num)
  }
}

end_time <- Sys.time()
time.taken <- end_time - start_time
print(time.taken)
```

Time difference of 14.54438 mins

The following are the distribution of R^2 s of the first two principal components of different combinations of emotions. The mean values are comparable to those of simple average constructs.

```
dist.selected <- ar1.r2.selected %>% my.dist.plot(col.names = c("PC1", "PC2"))

dist.selected
```


Now let's take a look at the best and worst combinations of emotions in terms of the average R^2 of the the first two principal components.

Table 2: The best selection of emotions yielding the highest R^2 s after PCA

BLIJ	ONTSP	OPGEW	DROEV	KWAAD	ANGST	DEPRI	STRES	R2.C1	R2.C2	R2.avg
1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.3293210	0.3005544	0.3149377
1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.3304309	0.2982086	0.3143197
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.3257625	0.3019865	0.3138745
1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.3277175	0.2982721	0.3129948
1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.3267111	0.2957162	0.3112136
1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.3246898	0.2972548	0.3109723

Table 3: The worst selection of emotions yielding the lowest R^2 s after PCA

BLIJ	ONTSP	OPGEW	DROEV	KWAAD	ANGST	DEPRI	STRES	R2.C1	R2.C2	R2.avg
0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.2875770	0.2453480	0.2664625
0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.2894606	0.2481166	0.2687886
0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.2905519	0.2496221	0.2700870
0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.2941507	0.2472965	0.2707236
0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.2932880	0.2490388	0.2711634
0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.2749504	0.2704285	0.2726895

I then run PCA over the best and worst combinations of emotions to find the first two (and, for the former, also the first three) principal components.

```
# First selecting the emotions and leaving out the redundant columns
data.pca <- data.primary %>% select(BLIJ:STRES)

# PCA on the selected emotions with the highest R2
sample.pca.high.2 <- data.pca %>% select(-ONTSP,-STRES) %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=2)
sample.pca.high.3 <- data.pca %>% select(-ONTSP,-STRES) %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=3)

# PCA on the selected emotions with the lowest R2
sample.pca.low.2 <- data.pca %>% select(ONTSP,STRES) %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=2)
sample.pca.low.3 <- data.pca %>% select(ONTSP,STRES) %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=3)
```

The following are the loadings of the principal components on the emotions.

Table 4: Component loadings of the first 2 principal components of the best constructs of emotions

	PC1	PC2
BLIJ	0.5824856	-0.2299068
OPGEW	0.6003595	-0.5202220
DROEV	-0.3178308	-0.4359476
KWAAD	-0.2532104	-0.4200379
ANGST	-0.1924700	-0.3724643
DEPRI	-0.3132130	-0.4138842

Table 5: Component loadings of the first 3 principal components of the best constructs of emotions

	PC1	PC2	PC3
BLIJ	0.5824856	-0.2299068	0.7768083
OPGEW	0.6003595	-0.5202220	-0.6062632
DROEV	-0.3178308	-0.4359476	0.0854775
KWAAD	-0.2532104	-0.4200379	0.0685588
ANGST	-0.1924700	-0.3724643	0.1068769
DEPRI	-0.3132130	-0.4138842	0.0747289

Table 6: Component loadings of the 2 principal components of the worst constructs of emotions

	PC1	PC2
ONTSP	-0.7340940	0.6790479
STRES	0.6790479	0.7340940

I also run PCA over the whole dataset and report the loadings. It's easy to compare the PCA loadings with the *loadings* imposed by simple averaging in `data.avg.simple`.

```
sample.pca.simple.2 <- data.pca %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=2)
sample.pca.simple.3 <- data.pca %>% na.omit %>% prcomp(rank=3)
```

Table 7: Component loadings of the first 2 principal components of all of the emotions

	PC1	PC2
BLIJ	0.4658216	-0.3441192
ONTSP	0.4680046	-0.0383668
OPGEW	0.4288116	-0.6045340
DROEV	-0.2593427	-0.2592807
KWAAD	-0.2244627	-0.2965214
ANGST	-0.1774848	-0.2817957
DEPRI	-0.2597153	-0.2529448
STRES	-0.4043606	-0.4648735

Table 8: Component loadings of the first 3 principal components of all of the emotions

	PC1	PC2	PC3
BLIJ	0.4658216	-0.3441192	0.0283066
ONTSP	0.4680046	-0.0383668	-0.6613306
OPGEW	0.4288116	-0.6045340	0.3196631
DROEV	-0.2593427	-0.2592807	-0.3810008
KWAAD	-0.2244627	-0.2965214	-0.2516564
ANGST	-0.1774848	-0.2817957	-0.1996611
DEPRI	-0.2597153	-0.2529448	-0.3474078
STRES	-0.4043606	-0.4648735	0.3010097

Comparing affect constructs

In order to get an idea about the “*most informative*” affect construct we need to compare different constructs built upon our data. Based on the PCA loadings, *Stijn* proposed that the best construct could be similar to $POSA + NEGA$ (SUMS) and $POSA - NEGA$ (DIFS) where POSA and NEGA from the simple average of the 3 + 5 emotions.

Comparing distribution of R^2 s

Here I plot the distribution of R^2 for POSA and NEGA as well as SUMS and DIFS along with distribution of R^2 for all the different combinations of emotions.

```
data.avg.diffs <- data.avg.simple
tmp.colnames <- data.avg.simple %>% colnames()
tmp.colnames.len <- tmp.colnames %>% length()

colnames(data.avg.diffs) <- c(tmp.colnames[1:(tmp.colnames.len-2)], "SUMS", "DIFS")

data.avg.diffs$SUMS <- data.avg.simple$POSA + data.avg.simple$NEGA
data.avg.diffs$DIFS <- data.avg.simple$POSA - data.avg.simple$NEGA
```

Table 9: data.avg.diffs: data frame of SUMS and DIFS built out of data.avg.simple

PID	BEEP	WAVE	MISS	SUMS	DIFS
101	1	1	0	73.46667	63.86667
101	2	1	0	61.46667	43.86667
101	3	1	0	67.20000	54.80000
101	4	1	1	NA	NA
101	5	1	0	68.33333	58.33333
101	6	1	0	53.86667	25.46667

```

results.avg.simple <- data.avg.simple %>% my.ar.r2(return.means = F) %>% na.omit()
results.avg.diffs <- data.avg.diffs %>% my.ar.r2(return.means = F) %>% na.omit()

dist.avg.simple <- results.avg.simple %>% my.dist.plot(col.names = c("POSA", "NEGA"))
dist.avg.diffs <- results.avg.diffs %>% my.dist.plot(col.names = c("SUMS", "DIFS"))

gridExtra::grid.arrange(dist.avg.simple, dist.avg.diffs, dist.selected, ncol=1)

```


Correlations

For a bit of more insight, let's look out correlations between POSA, NEGA, SUMS, DIFS, and best and worst PC1 and PC2. All the p-values are extremely significant.

```

cons1 <- data.avg.simple %>% select(POSA, NEGA) %>% na.omit() %>% as.matrix()
cons2 <- data.avg.diffs %>% select(SUMS, DIFS) %>% na.omit() %>% as.matrix()

data.high.2 <- data.pca %>% select(-ONTSP, -STRES)
cons3 <- scale(data.high.2, sample.pca.high.2$center, sample.pca.high.2$scale) %*%
  sample.pca.high.2$rotation %>% na.omit() %>% as.matrix()

data.low.2 <- data.pca %>% select(ONTSP, STRES)
cons4 <- scale(data.low.2, sample.pca.low.2$center, sample.pca.low.2$scale) %*%
  sample.pca.low.2$rotation %>% na.omit() %>% as.matrix()

colnames(cons3) <- c("best.PC1", "best.PC2")
colnames(cons4) <- c("worst.PC1", "worst.PC2")

constructs <- cbind(cons1, cons2, cons3, cons4)
constructs %>% cor(use= "na.or.complete") %>% corplot(method = "square", type = "upper")

```


Conclusions

Looks like we've got some good insights now. Let's talk and discuss the results!

Cheers!